

Implementation of agro-technology to support sustainable food self-sufficiency

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Why should we support sustainable food self-sufficiency?

PROCEEDING OF INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP AND SEMINAR

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Rice Production in Indonesia (million ton)

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Target	73.445	76.226	78.132	80.085	82.078
Realization	75.398	79.353	81.385		

(Source: BPS is processed by the Directorate General of Food Crops, 2018)

Rice production and consumption in Java, January - March 2018 (Source: ICRR, 2018)

Area	Month	Production		Consumption		Surplus, ton
		Dry unhusked rice, ton	Rice, ton	Population, indiv.	Rice, ton	
West Java	January	566,286.00	355,288.00	47,379,389.00	341,605.00	13,683.00
	February	1,245,797.00	781,613.00	47,379,389.00	341,605.00	440,008.00
	March	1,893,461.00	1,187,958.00	47,379,389.00	341,605.00	846,353.00
Central Java	January	620,690.00	389,421.00	34,019,095.00	214,660.00	174,761.00
	February	1,896,497.00	1,189,862.00	34,019,095.00	214,660.00	975,202.00
	March	1,817,796.00	1,140,485.00	34,019,095.00	214,660.00	925,825.00
East Java	January	428,610.00	268,910.00	39,075,152.00	265,711.00	3,199.00
	February	1,350,193.00	847,111.00	39,075,152.00	265,711.00	581,400.00
	March	2,026,739.00	1,271,574.00	39,075,152.00	265,711.00	1,005,863.00

A serious threat to agriculture

Soil organic matter is one of the key strategies to maintain the sustainability of soil quality / soil health

The agricultural system can be sustainable if the SOM content is > 2% (Loveland 2001).

Climate change impacts on crop yields → staple food crops were vulnerable to the impacts of climate change

- Model simulation results use daily weather data in **Latin America and Africa**, predicting a decline in corn yields of around 10% by 2055, equivalent to losing 2 billion \$ per year (Jones & Thornton, 2003).

- DSSAT model shows that during the main and off growing seasons, increase in temperature and changes rainfall pattern in **Malaysia** can be expected to reduce the rice yield by 12 and 31.3%, respectively, until the year 2030 (Vaghefi et al., 2016).

- **South Sumatera, Indonesia**, had decreasing wetland paddy, upland paddy, corn and soybean production, respectively with an average 9.44, 22.00, 10.7 and 10.10% per year (Ruminta et al., 2018)

Decreasing of Paddy, Corn and Soybean Production Due to Climate Change in Indonesia (Ruminta et al., 2018)

- Climate change influence crops through its effects on the growing, development and yield
- The objective of this study was to assess level of climate change risk in staple food crops production (paddy, corn and soybean)
- Research has been conducted in South Sumatera, Indonesia
- The results of this study indicate that staple food crops were vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, indicated by hazards such as decreasing production of paddy, corn and soybean **due to air temperature increase and rainfall change**
- Generally, South Sumatera had decreasing **wetland of paddy, upland paddy, corn and soybean production**, respectively with an average **9.44, 22.00, 10.7 and 10.10% per year**.

Soil Organic Management to increase C-stock (C-sequestration) and reduce greenhouse gas emissions

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1. Zero waste on integrated farming systems: quail livestock - catfish - vermiculture - organic vegetables (Dewi et al., 2014)

2. Empowering farmers in utilizing organic waste to diversify earthworm livestock products (Dewi et al., 2016)

3. Integration of varieties, biochar, and Azollae to obtain high-yielding and low GHG emission rice (Dewi et al., 2017)

We need to combine various qualities of organic matter

Nama Lokal	Nama Latin	Kecepatan pelapukan (persepsi petani)	C N L P				Nisbah		
			----- % -----				C/N	L/N	P/N
Lamtoro *	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	Cepat	42.1	3.00	13.0	1.94	14	4.3	0.6
Jengkol *	<i>Aithecelobium jiringa</i>	Sedang	49.8	3.50	35.0	2.40	14	10.0	0.7
Kayu hujan ^a	<i>Glicida sepium</i>	Cepat	52.9	3.20	32.0	1.12	17	10.0	0.4
Jati Thailand ^b	<i>Tectona grandiflora</i>	Belum diketahui	38.7	1.47	22.1	5.70	26	15.0	3.9
Mahoni ^c	<i>Swietenia mahogani</i>	Lama	36.1	1.79	19.7	34.60	20	11.0	19.3
Pohon Ramayana ^d	<i>Cassia spectabilis</i>	Belum diketahui	41.3	3.35	20.2	6.50	12	6.0	1.9
Kayu Afrika ^e	<i>Maesopsis emini</i>	Sedang	36.8	4.03	14.2	4.90	9	3.5	1.2
Gmelina *	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Belum diketahui	45.0	2.80	28.0	1.10	16	10.0	0.4

(Source: Hairiah et al., 2004)

The litter is categorized as easily decompose if the ratio of C: N <25, lignin content <15% and polyphenols <3% (Palm and Sanchez, 1991)

Nama Lokal	Nama Latin	Kecepatan pelapukan (persepsi petani)	C N L P				Nisbah		
			----- % -----				C/N	L/N	P/N
Mangga *	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Lama	36.0	2.20	20.0	3.10	20	10.0	1.4
Rambutan *	<i>Nephelium lappaceum</i>	Lama	56.2	2.00	20.0	2.40	28	10.0	1.2
Alpukat ^b	<i>Persea americana</i>	Sedang	40.4	1.58	14.7	34.70	26	9.3	22.0
Durian ^c	<i>Durio zibethinus</i>	Lama	35.3	1.75	25.3	2.30	20	14.5	1.3
Nangka *	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	Lama	45.0	3.20	32.0	0.63	14	10.0	0.2
Gandaria *	<i>Bouea macrophylla</i>	Belum diketahui	48.9	2.80	28.0	3.30	17	10.0	1.2
Belinjo, mlinjo ^d	<i>Gnetum gnemon</i>	Lama	42.1	2.36	7.3	6.50	18	3.1	2.8
Kemiri ^e	<i>Aleurites moluccana</i>	Lama	36.2	2.15	18.3	5.70	17	8.5	2.7

Source: Hairiah et al., 2004)

4. Water harvesting using 'embung mini' (Komariah et al. 2015)

- Constructed by Private or Group
- Farmer Empowerment of Conserving Water

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5. Water pump solar system (SPATS) (Apribowo et al., 2018)

Specifications:

- submersible pump with motor driver 48-220 Volt 300 W,
- 600 Wp Solar Panel,
- Pure Sine wave 2000 W inverter,
- MPPT Charge Controller,
- NYHY Power cable 2 x 2.5 mm 15 meters long,
- safety MCB box,
- HDPE pipe size 2 inch 10 meters long, iron frame and hard wheel.

43 SPATS debit is 15 - 20 m³ per day

Since climate change is affecting food and agriculture now and in the future, we need to increase the pace of adaptation and achieve additional mitigation benefits whenever possible (Vermeulen, 2014)

CROPS	LIVESTOCK	FISHERIES
<p>Switching to more abundant species</p>		
<p>Restoring degraded habitats and breeding sites like mangroves</p>		
<p>Strengthening infrastructure such as ports and landing sites</p>		

(Source: Vermeulen, 2014)

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Best Management Practices → integrated plant, soil, water, pest and disease management

Sumatra and Kalimantan are predicted to become wetter while Java, Bali and Nusa Tenggara are likely to experience a drier climate (Plesse, 2015).

- ✓ Selection of high-yielding rice varieties and 'extreme conditions' tolerant :
 - Flood, Drought, Saline, and Acid tolerance
 - Pest and disease resistant
- ✓ Water use efficiency Technology
- ✓ The application of biotechnology and nanotechnology
- ✓ Two important information:
 - Weather information
 - Planting calendar information

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4. Conclusion

- ❑ Sustainability of food self-sufficiency must be maintained, even though we face severe threats of climate change, land degradation, and reduced productive land
- ❑ Technological innovations in agro-technologies will be key factors to satisfy future food demand
- ❑ We must be more severe with developed adaptation and mitigation technologies.

We must work together, and do our best according to our expertise to realize food sovereignty in Indonesia.

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